

Lacrimal Electropunctoplasty: A New and Simple Technique

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ABSTRACT

A new surgical technique is described for lacrimal obstruction due to punctal stenosis. The only specific material needed are a sterile wooden toothpick and an ultrafine needle electrode. A retrospective analysis was conducted of all patients undergoing the proposed technique by one surgeon from 2016 to 2023. A total of 19 patients underwent the procedure in an office setting. The average follow-up time was 6 months (range, 5 months to 1 year). All patients were satisfied with the result. Advantages of the technique include the easy of operation, minimal surgical instruments, no use of silicone lacrimal catheter, and a short execution time.

Keywords: Epiphora; Lacrimal punctal stenosis; Lacrimal obstruction; Punctoplasty; Silicone catheter

INTRODUCTION

Epiphora is a frequent cause of ophthalmic patient consultation. Tearing is due to either excessive tear production, inadequate tear drainage or paradoxical in dry eye syndromes. The treatment depends on the etiology of the epiphora [1-3].

Medical literature reports 8 to 12% the punctal stenosis as a cause of epiphora [4,5]. Its incidence may be higher in patients with chronic blepharitis, in those treated with various topical medications, including glaucoma eye drops, and especially in patients treated with some chemotherapy drugs [6,7]. Several methods have been utilized to measure the aperture size of the punctum [8,9].

Its diagnosis is mainly clinical and a reliable method is the inability to intubate the punctum with a 26 G lacrimal cannula without dilation [10]. Other criteria is a diameter of less than 0.3 mm [11].

METHODS

This was a retrospective analysis of 19 patients (26 eyes), seven bilateral, undergoing the proposed technique, performed by one surgeon (J.S.) starting from 2016 to 2023. Informed consent was obtained for each procedure, and the review adhered to the standards of the Declaration of Helsinki. Punctal stenosis was confirmed by negative reflux of compression of the lacrimal sac,[12] direct nostrils examination, inability to intubate the punctum with a 26 G cannula without dilation and Taste Test (TT) described further on the Discussion section. All patients were from the private practice of the senior author, and all surgeries were performed at the office under local anesthesia plus mild sedation. Topical antibiotic and steroid eye drops were instilled postoperatively

for ten days in decreasing doses. The follow-up visits were scheduled at 3, 10 days; 1, 2 and 3 months after the operation. Albeit there was no epiphora the intervened lacrimal punctum was dilated with a sterile wooden toothpick prior eye drops of anesthesia employing a slit lamp at each visit.

SURGICAL TECHNIQUE

The surgical procedure was performed under local anesthesia, with light oral sedation using 5-10 Valium, in the office setting under a surgical microscope. Topical proparacaine hydrochloride 0.5% eye drops were instilled first. Some drops of 5% povidone-iodine were put in the operative eye. The surgical site was cleaned with 10% povidone-iodine. Once the surgical field had been prepared, the periocular skin, eyelashes, and lid margins were blotted to remove excess iodine, thereby enhancing the adherence of the plastic drape. The ocular surface was washed out with saline solution. The lower lacrimal punctum was dilated and syringing confirmed the permeability of the tear duct. The area was infiltrated with lidocaine 2% with epinephrine 1:100.000 injected through the conjunctival side. Ten minutes were elapsed. The lower eyelid was retracted with the pinky finger. A sterilized wooden toothpick was introduced in the lower lacrimal canaliculus using the thumb and index fingers of the same hand (Figure 1A). An ultrafine needle Bovie disposable electrode ES 60 or similar with 6 watts of energy set in the Derm 942 Bovie unit was applied to the superior posterior wall of the canaliculus in 3 mm in length utilizing the other hand (Figure 1B). The gap was confirmed with the same toothstick and withdrawn.

Figure 1(A): A fine needle electrode is applied along the superior posterior wall of the inferior canaliculus which is protected with a sterilized wooden toothpick using the thumb and index fingers of the same hand.

Figure 1(B): An ultrafine needle Bovie disposable electrode ES 60 or similar with 6 watts of energy set in the Derm 942 Bovie unit was applied to the superior posterior wall of the canaliculus in 3 mm length utilizing the other hand. The gap was confirmed with the same toothstick and withdrawn.

RESULTS

A total of 19 patients (12 females, 7 males; mean age, 58 years; range, 48-74 years) underwent the described surgical technique. The procedure was done on both inferior canaliculi in 7 patients. The average follow-up time was 6 months (range, 5 months to 1 year). The evaluation consisted in the absence of epiphora evaluated by the patients themselves.

There were no complications. Four patients related dewy-eyed in an outdoor cold environment that were subsided with deep nasal inhalation of air flux, strong blinking and protective glasses.

Representative clinical photographs from one patient in this cohort can be seen in [Figure 2](#).

Figure 2(A): Preoperative and **(B)** postoperative at three months.

DISCUSSION

Several surgical methods have been reported to open a stenosed lacrimal punctum, all of them imply surgical scission of the posterior wall of the lacrimal papilla and insertion of a silicon stent for at least 3 months [13,14]. A non-invasive procedure is the insertion of perforated punctal plugs but the results are not conclusive. Lacrimal punctal plugs have been reported as an etiologic factor for canaliculitis [15,16]. Mitomycin C and suture placement have been used to avoid adherence to the cleaved borders of the punctum aperture [17,18].

The described surgical technique is simple, cheap, fast, safe, and effective. The borders made with a fine needle electrode are not sticky and a stent is not required. The epiphora vanishes immediately. In this cohort, the superior lacrimal punctum was untouched due to its insignificance in the lacrimal drainage [19,20].

As much or more important than the surgical option utilized is a correct diagnosis. Epiphora due to punctum impairment is a diagnosis by ruling out other causes such as eyelid malpositions, infections, subsacular obstructions, and nasal impediments. A methodic and quick way to evaluate lacrimal patency is to compress the lacrimal sac with a cotton swab. We have outlined the Taste Test (TT) to verify permeability. A tasteful eye drop is instilled, and the savor is detected before 5 minutes. If the patient has ageusia or the prior evaluations are doubtful a Jones test and/or lacrimal syringing are performed.

DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTERESTS

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